

Preliminary Results of the Optioneering Design Study for the EAGLES-300 core

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ABSTRACT

The EAGLES Consortium was established in Europe aiming at deploying by 2039 EAGLES-300, a ~300 MWe commercial LFR in the SMR segment with competitiveness, safety and sustainability as distinguishing features. To materialize this ambition, an optioneering study was launched, exploiting the strong expertise of the Consortium members. For the reactor core, compactness, ~1 breeding ratio and high technology readiness were taken as drivers. At the end of optioneering, several design choices were taken, and a preliminary configuration set which meets all the design objectives and constraints. A particular challenge was represented by the design of the shielding, required to protect the core supporting structure against radiation damage. Several options were investigated also numerically, screening the use of moderating and absorbing materials, trying to overcome traditional, bulky solutions (i.e., manifold rings of structural assemblies). A compact layout was found, using only a moderating material which abates the hard tail of the neutron spectrum more significantly than how much absorbers reduce the total neutron flux. The resulting configuration, although still passible of adaptations and changes in the subsequent conceptual and basic phases, indicates the feasibility of pursuing a design which complies with all the established criteria, thereby of substantiating the overall vision of the EAGLES Consortium.

Keywords: EAGLES-300; LFR; Core design; Shielding; Optioneering study

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing urgency for energy sources capable to overcome the challenges of climate change has recently spread a worldwide acknowledgement on the potentialities of nuclear power. In the European context, initiatives such as the EU SMR Industrial Alliance [1] have been launched to accelerate deployment, of nuclear systems, in the mentioned case with a focus on the small modular reactor (SMR) segment, covering both evolutionary (i.e., Generation III/III+) and innovative (Generation IV) design concepts. Within the EU SMR Industrial Alliance, one of the 9 reference projects – selected on the basis of their compliance to the vision of the initiative – is the EAGLES-300 reactor (named “EU-SMR-LFR” at the time of its selection), promoted by the EAGLES Consortium established between Ansaldo Nucleare and ENEA for Italy, RATEN for Romania and SCK CEN for Belgium.

EAGLES-300 is proposed as a lead-cooled fast reactor (LFR), with power rating of about 300 MWe and competitive energy prices, able to operate in cogeneration mode and within a closed nuclear fuel cycle. EAGLES-300 is also being designed by the Consortium in such a way to comply with licensing and market availability by 2039. All these features are selected, being recognized as enablers for the mandatory conditions for the system to significantly contribute to the actions against climate change: compliance with the energy transition roadmap; increased social acceptability (reduced costs and reduced waste); outreach beyond the electricity sector; fitness for replacement of coal-fueled power plants. Several of these features reverberate into operational and safety performance, with the associated targets and constraints which entered the design process, notably for the core.

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2. MAIN DESIGN OBJECTIVES AND CONSTRAINTS

In line with Generation IV keystones and with SMR economic philosophy, EAGLES-300 targets a wide variety of safety, sustainability and economical objectives which translate in relevant requirements for the core. Most notably:

- a compact layout to ensure high energy density and reduced reactor size;
- a close to iso-breeding condition to enhance sustainability;
- the broadest use of qualified, proven or known solutions (in priority order) to shorten the time to deployment.

In the rationalized design process established for EAGLES-300, all the identified performance targets and constraints have been translated into a hierarchy of objectives and requirements, which, from the highest levels qualitatively delimiting the design space, are flew down into a set of quantitative design criteria and limits.

Table I summarizes the main design targets and constraints adopted for EAGLES-300. The fuel temperature limit is referred to anticipated operational occurrences with an overpower factor, whereas the maximum allowable clad temperature (at mid-wall) is assumed 650 °C in steady state, by foreseeing it made of AIM1 stainless steel with an Al₂O₃ surface coating applied by pulsed laser deposition (PLD).

Table I. EAGLES-300 core design targets and constraints.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Thermal power	800	MW
Core inlet / outlet temperature	370 / 520	°C
Min sub-cycle length	14	Months
Fuel material	MOX (UO _{1.97} -PuO _{1.97})	-
Max Pu enrichment	30	wt.%
Peak fuel burnup	120	MWd/kg _{HM}
Max fuel temperature in NO/AOO	2800	°C
Clad and wrapper material	AIM1	-
Corrosion protection barrier	Al ₂ O ₃ coating by PLD	-
Pins spacing	grids	-
Max cladding dose	100	DPA
Max clad temperature in steady state	650	°C
Sub-criticality at shutdown	0.99	-
Sub-criticality at refueling	0.95	-
Max coolant velocity	2	m/s
Max core pressure drop	0.2	MPa
Inner vessel material	316LN SS	-
Max inner vessel dose	10	DPA

3. CORE DESIGN OPTIONEERING RESULTS

Starting from the established design basis and leveraging the extensive experience built by the EAGLES Consortium on fast reactors design, optioneering was done, out of which general and particular design choices were taken, including firm ones (e.g., reliance on hexagonal assemblies arranged in a triangular lattice). The outcome of the optioneering led to the candidate core configuration shown in *Figure 1*.

3.1. FA design, core layout and neutronic modelling

The left frame of *Figure 1* depicts the fuel assembly (FA) design proposed for the EAGLES-300 core, having 127 MOX-fueled pins enclosed by a steel hexagonal wrapper. The design of the fuel pin was maintained as in the Advanced Lead Fast Reactor European Demonstrator (ALFRED) concept [2] but:

- the fissile length was increased from 81 cm up to 130 cm;
- the pin pitch was decreased by 0.1 mm and fixed at 13.5 mm, resulting in a wrapper internal flat-to-flat distance of 155 mm and a subassembly pitch of 166 mm in the core (including 3.5 mm wrapper thickness and 4 mm bypass among FAs).

Figure 1. Preliminary FA design (left) and core map (right) of EAGLES-300.

The right frame of *Figure 1* shows the EAGLES-300 core layout at the equilibrium as preliminarily simulated with the ERANOS deterministic code [3]. The cross-sections of the different core regions were produced in a 1968 energy-group structure and condensed to 33 groups by the ECCO cell code [4]. The macroscopic cross-sections were used for the ERANOS full-core calculations, performed by the TGV module [5] adopting the variational-nodal method [6] in a 3D hexagonal geometry model of the system. The most up-to-date nuclear data library ENDF/B-VIII.0 was used, prepared in a special format readable by ECCO/ERANOS (which does not accept libraries in the standard ENDF-6 format) [7].

For radial power flattening, the 223 FAs were divided in three zones: inner (31 FAs), middle (84 FAs) and outer (108 FAs) with 15.5, 17.0 and 21.5 wt.% Pu enrichment, respectively. The fissile zone is surrounded by one ring of dummy assemblies, having the same design of the FA but with yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ) pellets into the AIM1 clads. The dummies are inserted both for neutron economy (as radial reflectors) and to shield the cylindrical inner vessel surrounding the core.

An irradiation cycle made of 4 batches and 14 months at full power of sub-cycle length was investigated, whereas 1/4 of irradiated fuel (the one achieving the target burnup) is replaced by a batch of fresh fuel during the periodic shutdowns (for refueling and maintenance). By adopting the one-batch approach – consistently with the pre-conceptual status of the design investigation – the average fuel residence times in the core result to be 21 and 35 months at the beginning and end of each irradiation sub-cycle (BoC and EoC, respectively), defining the [BoC, EoC] equilibrium sub-cycle.

Under these simplifications, the core layout of *Figure 1* was established. It is important to remark that an over-criticality of about 0.8% was maintained at this stage, in order to consider the detrimental effect on the core reactivity of the protections that will be inserted to shield the inner vessel, analyzed in section 4 and non-yet taken into account to this point.

3.2. Control and safety devices

For the control and safety devices, in these preliminary evaluations the design foreseen in ALFRED for the 12 control rods (CRs) and the 6 safety devices (SDs) was maintained (see *Figure 1*), with longer absorbing parts (and re-dimensioned for the 1 mm core pitch reduction). The CRs are inserted in the core from the bottom and are also provided with an electromagnetic lockage which can be released to allow the passive insertion (by buoyancy) of the bundle into the core, thereby assigning to the CRs bank the role of first scram system. The 6 SDs are inserted from the bottom as well, but they are based on a different design and insertion mode to fulfill the diversity requirement. In both safety systems, the boron carbide (B₄C) enriched in ¹⁰B was used as absorbing material. In some details:

- the absorbing part of the CR is divided in two axial zones enriched at 42% and 90% in ^{10}B , used for the control and shutdown function, respectively;
- the absorbing material of the SD is enriched at 90% in ^{10}B ;
- the control function, used also for the reactor start-up and power tuning, can compensate the k_{eff} swing in the equilibrium sub-cycle, that is ~ 1200 pcm in 14 months;
- the scram functions of the CRs and the SDs can satisfy the sub-criticality requirements for shutdown and refueling (1000 and 5000 pcm, respectively, as in PWRs; see *Table I*), even by considering single failures and large uncertainty margins.

3.3. Power distributions and burnup performances

By adopting three fuel zones, an excellent radial power flattening was obtained in the equilibrium core. *Table II* reports the power peaking factors at BoC and EoC: the core-wise FA distribution factor (FADF), the assembly-wise fuel pin distribution factor (FPDF) in the hottest FAs of the three zones, the fuel pin axial factor (FPAF, in the hot pin of the hottest FAs) and the total peaking factor that is the product of the previous three values. Visual representations are shown in:

- *Figure 2* for the FADF at BoC and EoC;
- *Figure 3* and *Figure 4* for some examples of the FPDF and FPAF, respectively, in the hottest FAs of the inner and outer zones at BoC.

It can be observed the high degree of flattening among and inside the FAs. With a linear power rating in the hot pins lower than 350 W cm^{-1} , clad and fuel temperature constraints (see *Table I*) should be respected. Additionally, core pressure drops should, as well, respect the posed constraint.

Table II. Power distribution factors at BoC and EoC in the three fuel zones.

Power Distribution Factors	Inner zone		Middle zone		Outer zone	
	BoC	EoC	BoC	EoC	BoC	EoC
FADF	1.179	1.149	1.179	1.150	1.106	1.099
FPDF	1.013	1.013	1.017	1.015	1.052	1.049
FPAF	1.263	1.255	1.276	1.253	1.317	1.247
Total peaking factor	1.508	1.460	1.530	1.463	1.533	1.437

The burnup performance in the 56 months irradiation cycle reaches a close to iso-breeding condition, with a Pu burning rate limited to -3.2 kg/TWh and a minor actinide production limited to 1.8 kg/TWh . The reduced peaking factors resulting from the excellent radial flattening facilitate the respect of the constraints on the maximum fuel burnup and cladding damage (see *Table I*) even for the hottest pins.

Figure 2. Core-wise FADF at BoC (left) and EoC (right) with encircled hot FAs in the three zones.

Figure 3. Assembly-wise FPFD at BoC in the inner (left) and outer (right) zone.

Figure 4. Fuel pin-wise FPAF at BoC in the inner (left) and outer (right) zone.

4. SHIELDING DESIGN OPTIONEERING RESULTS

As explained in Section 2, the design requirements for the EAGLES-300 core specify that the maximum dose on the inner vessel should not exceed 10 dpa after 60 years of irradiation (see *Table I*). This constraint represents a significant challenge for a compact reactor configuration. To investigate the irradiation damage on the inner vessel and to assess the options for a dedicated neutron shield, several scoping simulations were performed using the deterministic ERANOS code.

It must be recalled that the ERANOS 3D hexagonal geometry model of the core adopted in Section 3 does not yet foresee the inner vessel shielding. In some details:

- the cylindrical inner vessel (made of 316L stainless steel) was modeled with 60 “virtual” assemblies representing a homogeneous mixture of steel and lead, to simulate this structure and the surrounding coolant in a hexagonal position of the core lattice;
- to simulate almost accurately the circular shape, 12 assemblies of pure lead coolant were also inserted between the dummies and the inner vessel;
- all around the simulated inner vessel, the downcomer is also modeled by “virtual” assemblies, made of pure lead at the 370 °C inlet temperature.

To capture the damage in the most realistic way on the inner vessel, the core geometry of *Figure 1* was modeled with a cylindrical geometry. This step was necessary since ERANOS is not able to represent simultaneously the hexagonal shape of the FAs and the cylindrical geometry of the inner vessel, unlike Monte Carlo codes.

Figure 5 shows the cylindrical models of the EAGLES-300 core without shield (left frame, corresponding to 3D hexagonal model adopted in Section 3) and with a 5 cm thick shield (right frame). The cylindrical models were implemented arranging the different regions of the core by preserving the overall mass in each region. The radial positions of the CRs and SDs were accurately reproduced, but still resulted the most penalizing approximation in terms of model accuracy, i.e. for the multiplication factor value. On the other hand, while in the 3D hexagonal model the inner vessel region is described as a mixture of

coolant and 316LN steel, this approach allows for its more realistic representation for the DPA analyses. Indeed, besides the correct cylindrical shape, the inner vessel can be modeled as being entirely composed of 316LN steel, thus providing a more accurate estimate of the irradiation damage in this structural material.

Figure 5. Radial layouts of the cylindrized core: configuration without shield (left), configuration with a 5 cm-thick shield composed of moderating and absorbing materials (right).

For the DPA calculation, few simplifying assumptions were introduced:

- DPA was evaluated only for Fe, Cr, and Ni, which together account for about 95 wt.% of the steel. This means that the actual DPA on the inner vessel is expected to be slightly higher than the values here shown;
- the reaction rates were assumed to be constant over time. The objective of this analysis is to estimate the DPA over 60 years of operation, rather than to provide a detailed time-dependent evolution. Since the reactor is expected to operate most of the time at (or close to) full power, with a relatively homogeneous neutron flux, this assumption is considered acceptable;
- a conservative condition was adopted by performing the calculation with the equilibrium core layout of 223 FAs (see Figure 1) with fresh fuel composition. Furthermore, the CRs were partially inserted as at BoC, yielding the highest neutron flux at core midplane in the outer core region (and hence in the inner vessel).

Comparing the k_{eff} results of the 3D hexagonal (Section 3) and the 2D cylindrical geometry models, a difference of about -460 pcm is observed, which, as anticipated, can be chiefly attributed to the cylindrization of the CR and SD absorber regions.

Table III. Comparison of irradiation damage (in DPA) on the inner vessel for the bare configuration and for a 5 cm-thick shield with different material compositions.

<i>Inner vessel DPA – 60 years</i>		
Shield composition	MAX	AVERAGE
Bare (no shield)	88.25	30.49
3 cm YH _{1.87} + 2 cm B ₄ C	11.23	3.70
3 cm YH _{1.87} + 2 cm borated steel	13.31	4.43
3 cm YH _{1.87} + 2 cm Eu ₂ O ₃	12.43	4.13
5 cm YH _{1.87}	9.53	3.08

As reported in the first row of Table III, the maximum DPA value for the bare core (i.e., without shield; see left frame of Figure 5) exceeds the design limit for the inner vessel. Trying to reduce the damage below 10 DPA, a 5 cm-thick shield was introduced (see right frame of Figure 5) by adopting cylindrical layers of moderating and absorbing materials with 3 and 2 cm thickness, respectively. Considering the limited room available for moderation, a hydride-based moderator was selected from the beginning, specifically yttrium dihydride with a hypo-stoichiometry of 1.87 (YH_{1.87}), chosen for its

favorable mechanical properties [8]. Three different absorbing materials were tested (natural boron carbide, borated steel and europium oxide) but none of these absorber configurations was able to keep the DPA below the design limit. As reported in the last row of *Table III*, the objective was achieved by a 5 cm thick shield entirely composed of the $\text{YH}_{1.87}$ moderator.

This outcome is justified by observing the radial flux profile for neutron energies relevant to radiation damage ($E > 0.1$ MeV), shown in *Figure 6*. It is evident that moderation is more effective in reducing radiation damage compared to absorption, considering the constraints of a compact reactor design, where only a few centimeters are available for the shielding region.

Figure 6. Radial flux profile for neutron energies relevant to irradiation damage ($E > 0.1$ MeV) for the bare configuration and for 5 cm-thick shield configurations with different material compositions.

Since the initial selection of a 5 cm shield was driven solely by the intention to match the thickness of the inner vessel, a further investigation was carried out through a parametric analysis of irradiation damage for different shield thicknesses composed entirely of $\text{YH}_{1.87}$. As summarized in *Table IV*, the results – exhibiting the expected exponential trend (*Figure 7*) – confirm that 5 cm represents the minimum thickness required to keep the vessel DPA below the design threshold. This candidate reference option impacts the reactivity of the core by about 0.7%, and is thus consistent with the allowance introduced in the core setup (0.8%, see Section 3.1).

Table IV. Parametric analysis of irradiation damage on the barrel/inner vessel as a function of shield thickness.

<i>Barrel/inner vessel DPA – 60 years</i>		
Shield Thickness	MAX	AVERAGE
bare (no shield)	88.25	30.49
3 cm $\text{YH}_{1.87}$	18.36	6.05
4 cm $\text{YH}_{1.87}$	13.10	4.27
5 cm $\text{YH}_{1.87}$	9.53	3.08
6 cm $\text{YH}_{1.87}$	7.06	2.26
7 cm $\text{YH}_{1.87}$	5.29	1.68

Figure 7. Trend of the maximum DPA on the inner vessel as a function of the shield thickness.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Despite the challenging targets set for the design of the EAGLES-300 core, a solution was found for an 800 MWth, almost iso-breeding configuration. 223 hexagonal FAs organized in 3 enrichment zones, and operation in a 4-batch strategy on a 56 equivalent full power months irradiation cycle, permit to achieve a critical core with extremely well flattened power distribution. Control and shutdown means – whose design was borrowed from that of ALFRED – provide wide margins to operate and protect the reactor. A compact shield configuration was also identified, relying solely on yttrium dihydride (YH_{1.87}), which permits protection of the inner vessel from radiation damage. All these encouraging outcomes, resulting from extensive optioneering studies and scoping analyses, increase confidence on the success of the more detailed engineering to be performed in the subsequent conceptual and basic design phases, thus on the achievement of the general targets of the EAGLES Consortium itself.

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